

YUFERING Project
YUFE TRANSFORMING R&I THROUGH EUROPE-WIDE
KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

Call: H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020
Topic: IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020
Funding type: Coordination and Support Action Lump Sum
Grant agreement No. 101016967

**D 6.2: Report on Collaboration with other consortia
of European Universities**

February 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101016967

Deliverable number	D 6.2
Deliverable name:	Report on Collaboration with other consortia of European Universities
WP number:	WP6
Version	V2
Delivery due date:	Project month 36 (29/02/2024)
Actual date of submission:	09/02/2024
Dissemination level:	Public
Number of pages:	6
Lead beneficiary:	Maastricht University (UM)
Deliverable leader:	Andreas Bressler (UM)
Author(s):	Andreas Bressler (UM)
Contributor(s):	Magdalena Kohl (YUFE Central Office - UM)
Reviewer(s)	Dorian Hayes (UEssex)

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List of Abbreviations and Definitions

CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
EC	European Commission
ECIU	European Consortium Innovative Universities
EPICUR	European Partnership for an Innovative Campus Unifying Regions
FOCI	Future-proof Criteria for Innovative European Education
FOREU	Informal Forum of European Universities Alliances
R&I	Research and innovation
SwafS	Science with and for Society
YUFE	Young Universities for the Future of Europe

Table of Contents

1. Section: Introduction	4
2. Section: Reporting on subtasks	4
3. Section: Conclusions	6
4. References	6

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Report on collaboration with other consortia of European Universities

1. Section: Introduction

The purpose of this document is to report on the task for exploitation of project results through exchange of best practices with other funded European University consortia. The focus of this document is to report on the outcomes for the different subtasks. This task is a deliverable of YUFERING WP6 'dissemination, exploitation, communication'. The main objective of this task was to deepen the connections and collaboration with other funded European University consortia.

2. Section: Reporting on subtasks

Subtask 1: Participate in the joint Forum of European University alliances (FOREU) that will be jointly organized by the 17 alliances that have been selected under the first Erasmus+ pilot call in 2019.

The forum will focus on the sharing of best practice examples and experienced drivers of success and will allow for exchange on legal, financial and regulatory barriers identified at the different levels (local, regional, and European). The forum will equally allow for identifying solutions to circumvent or minimize their impact on the emerging European Research Area.

The YUFERING management and the YUFE central office have actively participated in the FOREU core group and the subgroup dedicated to research and innovation (R&I). Via this group, YUFE has contributed to informal input on position papers towards the European Commission (EC) and the wider education sector on where to focus common efforts, as well as funding, in the future.

The YUFERING project was present at the SwafS cross-alliance forum 2023 on R&I in European Universities Alliances in Brussels in November 2023. Twenty-three European university alliances presented their ongoing and completed R&I projects during round tables, workshops and presentations. Topics ranged from the development of a common R&I agenda and action plan to dialogues focused on mainstreaming Open Science practices. Dr. Eva M. Méndez Rodríguez (UC3M), YUFERING work package leader on Open Science, represented YUFERING in a workshop on reforming research evaluation.

Eva presented the work that YUFERING has done over the last years on Open Science. Her talk focused on the achievements on common Open Science practices and policies, indicators of Open Science performance, bottom up Open Science implementations and connections with the CoARA goals. She engaged the audience in an open discussion on questions of who is responsible for making research open, and how the participants' institutions implement the CoARA goals.

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Beyond joint FOREU activities and efforts, the YUFE Alliance organized own dissemination events engaging other Alliances, such as the first strategic dialogue on European universities 2023, and the YUFE town hall meeting 2023. During the strategic dialogue on European universities, partners from the European University Initiative presented and discussed their best practices and common challenges. The YUFE town hall gathered all internal and external YUFE stakeholders to discuss the impact and contribution of the European Universities to its stakeholders, higher education systems and societies.

Subtask 2: Explore a more structured form of collaboration with the two other alliances, namely ECIU and EPICUR (via EPIconnect).

Beyond the FOREU network, YUFE is in close (bilateral) contact with several Alliances. YUFE, ECIU and EPICUR are still closely connected, working together at various levels, exchanging experiences, and good practices. This connection is facilitated by EPIconnect, an EPICUR platform catering to network-to-network relations, supported by digital collaboration tools. While the initial conversations of the three first generation alliances focused on possible collaboration in the form of R&I, the conversations have led to fruitful collaboration in another areas, such as the FOCI (Future-proof Criteria for Innovative European Education) work on the European Degree (Label).

The collaboration between YUFE, ECIU and EPICUR is also continued in the FOCI consortium. The aim of FOCI is to address several all-encompassing challenges, such as the human, technical, data, education, R&I aspects that come with cohesive, cross-border and interdisciplinary education. Its main aim is to work in a common effort on the European Degree (Label), which happened in response to a policy experimentation call launched by the EC under Erasmus+.

While the YUFERING project will be finalized in spring 2024, YUFE is looking into possibilities for continuing the fruitful collaboration of the three Alliances in other projects in future. One direction that YUFE would like to explore is linking the findings on a European Degree (Label) at Bachelor and Master level to the YUFE approach to doctoral and postdoctoral training. This is under development in the YUFE 2030 Erasmus+ and YUFE4Postdoc projects.

Taken together, the different projects run in cooperation between the alliances in the fields of education and R&I are leading to closer links between the alliances' missions, and allowing our universities to transform and advance in both aspects.

In parallel, bottom-up collaboration on different topics, such as Open Science, was established among Alliances and upon initiative of the different experts. Such networks have not initially been foreseen by in the YUFERING proposal but may find a home in a proposal for a FOREU community of practice that will be submitted in response to an Erasmus+ call in February 2024.

Subtask 3: Work towards establishing connections with national platforms in different European countries, in which the YUFE universities are places and exchange

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information on progress made with other members of European University alliances placed in the same countries.

While establishing deeper connections with the national platforms in the home countries of the YUFE partners remains an important goal, we have to conclude that this goal was too ambitious for the current state of YUFE and the duration of YUFERING. We concluded that before reaching outward, it is important to establish a YUFE internal research network and stronger connections with other European university alliances. Partners and researchers are all part of various national research and policy networks. By tapping into those existing structures in the future we can prevent establishing redundant channels and represent the YUFE R&I interests more effectively, and build new national platforms where needed.

An example of the research network initiatives are the bottom-up connections between the Deans of Law, Deans of Health and Life Sciences and Deans of History. In their respective connections, they are exchanging best practices and work on plans for joint research and education projects. This has led to the initiation of BioYUFE, a cooperation of the biology, bioscience and life science faculties of the YUFE partner universities. BioYUFE offers master students of the participating faculties to take shared (online and hybrid) elective courses.

3. Section: Conclusions

In conclusion, the efforts undertaken by YUFE to connect with other alliances have yielded important outcomes. Through active participation in initiatives such as FOREU and the SwafS cross-alliance forum 2023, YUFE has strengthened its ties within the European University Alliances, fostering collaboration and sharing best practices.

The direct collaboration between YUFE, ECIU and EPICUR in R&I has broadened the scope of cooperation and led to cooperation on the topic of the European Degree Label in the FOCI consortium.

Although the goal of establishing connections with national platforms in the YUFE partner countries proved too ambitious within the current state and timeframe, the emphasis on building a robust YUFE internal research network and utilizing existing national networks ensures a more effective representation of YUFE's R&I interests in the future.

4. References

1. European Commission, Research Executive Agency, 2020. Grant Agreement 101016967.

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